
WORKING STATUS OF MIGRANT WORKERS: A CASE STUDY OF CHHATTISGARH

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.7648168

Abstract:

Generally, people migrate in search of employment or for better livelihood from one place to another place. They are the important segment of any country's economy hence the migrant workers have a fair share in the process of development. According to their skill and working experience they are engaged various types of works. This paper tries to understand the engagement of the migrants in various types of works in the state of Chhattisgarh. The available secondary data of census 2011 is used to assess the employment engagement of these workers as per their age group. It is observed that a large percentage of migrants in Chhattisgarh are engaged as main workers and are in the age group of 35 to 39. Due to the enforcement of act of child prohibition in hazardous work, the engagement of children in the age group of 0 to 14 is very less. The same kind of results have been observed in this paper. It is also observed that most of the migrants in the state of Chhattisgarh are not engaged in any kind of work, hence are classified as non-workers. In the category of marginal workers, the highest percentage engagement is of those migrants who are in the age group of 20 to 24 age. This paper tries to fill the gap of studies conducted in the work engagement of migrants according to their age groups.

Keywords: Migrants, Chhattisgarh, Main workers, Marginal Workers, Non-Workers

Introduction:

Chhattisgarh State Migrant Workers Policy 2020 clarifies that 'migrant labourer' means a worker who volunteered to migrate from his place of residence, interstate or intrastate or through a contractor, agent, (a member of the family

or the entire family or more than one Members migrate). The said migration may be of a seasonal, permanent or temporary nature (Chhattisgarh Jansampark News, 2021). The Preamble of Chhattisgarh State Migrant Workers Policy 2020 states that Chhattisgarh is an

agricultural state rich in natural resources and forest produce. Agriculture, forest produce and wages are the basis of livelihood of most of the residents here. As Chhattisgarh has 'single crop farming' culture, the small and marginal farmers as well as the agricultural laborers migrate to other states for livelihood (Chhattishgarh Jansampark News, 2021).

In the states of Chhattisgarh, states government started a number of program and initiative. For protection, welfare and social security of the migrant workers, Chhattisgarh Government's Labour Department has formulated Chhattisgarh State Migrant Workers Policy 2020. Notification in this regard has been issued by the Labour Department (AVDHESH MALLICK, 2021). For smooth and safe migration of the migrant workers, Labour Department in coordination with various departments such as Revenue, Panchayat and Rural Development Department, Skill Development Authority, Employment Planning, Department of Industries, Health, Finance and Home has formulated the policy for migrant workers to provide them better employment opportunities through registration and database compilation. Despite of a lots of workers migrate to other developed state for employment or better opportunities (Murali & Afifi, 2014).

According to the census of India migrant workers are engaged into main workers, marginal workers and non-workers. According to their skill and working experience they are engaged various types of works according to their age groups. Migrant labour is an important foundation of nation building. The migrant workers have a fair share in the development of the migrant state as well as the native state. But despite the valuable contribution, migrant workers have to face exploitation and difficulties in the migrant state. A rich amount of literature suggested Chhattisgarh state have a huge amount of migrant's worker those who are engaged in various work category as one of the potential works for carrying out the research. This paper tries to fill the gap of studies conducted in the work engagement of migrants according to their age groups. The study is an attempt to understand the working status of migrant workers according to their age group in Chhattisgarh.

Study Area:

Chhattisgarh lies between 17°47' and 24°06'N latitude and 80°15' and 84°24'E longitude. The state measures 640 km from north to south and 336 km from east to west.

Chhattisgarh is a landlocked and heavily forested state located in the region of Central India. Formerly part of Madhya Pradesh it was granted statehood on 1 November 2000. The newly formed state is surrounded by six states namely- Uttar Pradesh, Jharkhand, Orissa, Andhra Pradesh, Maharashtra and Madhya Pradesh. The 16 districts of Chhattisgarh are divided into three divisions It is the 9th-largest state in India, with an area of 135,192 km². As of 2021, it has a population of roughly 30 million, making it the 17th most populated state in the country. Chhattisgarh has a tropical climate. It is hot and humid in the summer because of its proximity to the Tropic of Cancer and its dependence on the monsoons for rains. Chhattisgarh has four-

lane or two-lane roads that provide connectivity to major cities. A total of 11 national highways pass through the state, together measuring 3,078 km (Wikipedia contributors, 2022).

Material and Methods:

In this paper we used the available secondary data of census of India 2011. The Indian Census is the largest single source of a variety of statistical information on different characteristics of the people of India. This data has been used to assess the employment engagement of these workers as per their age group in Chhattisgarh state of India. As per census of India, migrant workers are classified into main workers, marginal workers and non-workers. According to

their skill and working experience they are engaged in various types of works. We have examined the highest and the least

percentage of engagement of migrant workers according to their age group categories in various types of works.

Figure.1 Types of migrant workers according to census of India, 2011

Results:

Percentage of main workers to the total migrants:

Table 1 shows the percentage of main workers to the total migrants of Chhattisgarh from all duration of residence in 2011. The highest percentage of total main workers were in 35 to 39 age group

categories, secondly were in 40 to 59 age group category and thirdly were in 30 to 34 age group category and least percentage of total main workers were in 0 to 14 age group category and about 40 percentage of total main workers migrants to the total migrants of Chhattisgarh did not count in any specific age group.

Table: 1
Chhattisgarh: Percentage of main workers to the total migrants, 2011
(All duration of Residence)

Age-group	Main Workers		
	Persons	Males	Females
0-14	2.1	2.0	2.1
15-19	23.6	22.7	24.2
20-24	38.3	53.5	34.7
25-29	46.1	78.7	38.1
30-34	52.4	88.4	42.6
35-39	55.7	90.8	44.5
40-59	54.9	89.9	42.9
60+	24.5	47.7	18.7
Age not stated	40.0	50.9	33.4

The highest percentage of male main workers were in 35 to 39 age group categories, secondly were in 40 to 59 age group category and thirdly were in 30 to 34 age group category and least percentage of male main workers were reported in 0 to 14 age group category and about 51 percentage of male main workers migrants to the total migrants of Chhattisgarh did not count in any specific age group. The highest percentage of female main workers were in 35 to 39 age group category, secondly highest main workers were in 40 to 59 age group category and thirdly were in 30 to 34 age group category and least percentage of female main workers were in 0 to 14 age group category and about 33 percentage of female main workers migrants to the total migrants of Chhattisgarh did not count any specific

age group, that means they did not tell their ages.

Percentage of Marginal Workers to the total migrants:

Table 2 shows the percentage of marginal workers to the total migrants of Chhattisgarh from all duration of residence in 2011. The highest percentage of total marginal workers were in 20 to 24 age group categories, secondly were in 25 to 29 age group category and thirdly were in 30 to 34 age group category and least percentage of total marginal workers were in 0 to 14 age group category and about 15 percentage of total marginal workers migrants to the total migrants of Chhattisgarh did not report any specific age group.

Table: 2

Chhattisgarh: Percentage of Marginal Workers to the total migrants, 2011

(All duration of Residence)

Age-group	Marginal Worker		
	Person	Male	Female
0-14	2.1	1.6	2.7
15-19	18.8	8.3	25.0
20-24	26.6	10.0	30.6
25-29	25.8	9.4	29.8
30-34	25.0	7.7	29.7
35-39	23.3	7.0	28.5
40-59	21.6	5.9	27.0
60+	14.1	7.6	15.7
Age not stated	15.1	7.1	19.9

The highest percentage of male marginal workers were in 20 to 24 age group categories, secondly were in 25 to 29 age group category and thirdly were in 15 to 19 age group category and least percentage of male marginal workers were in 0 to 14 age group category and about 7 percentage of male marginal workers migrants to the total migrants of Chhattisgarh did not count in any specific age group. The highest percentage of female marginal workers were in 20 to 24 age group categories, secondly were in 25 to 29 age group category and thirdly were in 30 to 34 age group category and least percentage of female marginal workers were in 0 to 14 age group category and about 20 percentage of female marginal workers migrants to the total migrants of

Chhattisgarh did not count in any specific age group, that means they did not tell their ages.

Percentage of Non-Workers to the total migrants:

Table 3 shows the percentage of non-workers to the total migrants of Chhattisgarh from all duration of residence in 2011. The highest percentage of total non-workers were in 0 to 14 age group categories, secondly were in 60 or more age group category and thirdly were in 15 to 19 age group category and least percentage of total non-workers were in 35 to 39 age group category and about 45 percentage of total non-workers migrants to the total migrants of Chhattisgarh did not appear in any specific age group.

Table: 3

**Chhattisgarh: Percentage of Non-Workers to the total migrants, 2011
(All duration of Residence)**

Age-group	Percentage of Non-Workers		
	Person	Male	Female
0-14	95.8	96.4	95.2
15-19	57.6	69.1	50.8
20-24	35.0	36.5	34.7
25-29	28.1	11.8	32.1
30-34	22.6	4.0	27.6
35-39	21.0	2.2	27.0
40-59	23.5	4.2	30.1
60+	61.4	44.7	65.6
Age not stated	44.9	42.0	46.6

The highest percentage of male non-workers were in 0 to 14 age group categories, secondly were in 15 to 19 age

group category and thirdly were in 60 or more age group category and least percentage of male non-workers were in

35 to 39 age group category and about 42 percentage of male non-workers migrants to the total migrants of Chhattisgarh did not count in any specific age group. The highest percentage of female non-workers were in 0 to 14 age group categories, secondly were in 60 or more age group category and thirdly were in 15 to 19 age group category and least percentage of female non-workers were in 35 to 39 age group category and about 47 percentage of female non-workers migrants to the total

migrants of Chhattisgarh did not count any specific age group, that means they did not tell their ages.

Main workers, Marginal workers and non-workers to the total migrants:

Table 4 shows the number and percentage of main workers, marginal workers and non-workers to the total migrants of Chhattisgarh from all duration of residence by age group wise during 2011.

Table: 4
Chhattisgarh
Main workers, Marginal workers and non-workers to the total migrants, 2011
(All duration of Residence)

Age-group	Total migrants	Main workers	Percentage	Marginal workers	Percentage	Non workers	Percentage
0-14	6,60,277	13,610	2.06	14,109	2.14	6,32,558	95.8
15-19	3,80,811	89,872	23.6	71,485	18.77	2,19,454	57.63
20-24	7,37,933	2,82,877	38.33	1,96,510	26.63	2,58,546	35.04
25-29	8,23,855	3,79,681	46.09	2,12,590	25.8	2,31,584	28.11
30-34	8,29,456	4,34,408	52.37	2,07,761	25.05	1,87,287	22.58
35-39	7,65,162	4,26,232	55.7	1,78,069	23.27	1,60,861	21.02
40-59	18,82,201	10,33,092	54.89	4,07,215	21.64	4,41,894	23.48
60+	8,20,350	2,00,708	24.47	1,15,772	14.11	5,03,870	61.42
Age not stated	7,154	2,860	39.98	1,081	15.11	3,213	44.91

The highest number of total migrants of Chhattisgarh from all duration of residence were in 40 to 59 age group categories. Second highest number of total migrant workers of Chhattisgarh were in 30 to 34 age group, thirdly were in 20 to 29 age group categories and least number of total migrant workers of Chhattisgarh

were in 15 to 19 age group categories and 7,157 total migrant workers did not record any specific age group that means they did not tell their particular age to the interviewers. Now we are coming on main worker migrants of total migrants of Chhattisgarh. The highest percentage of main worker migrants to the total migrants

of Chhattisgarh were in 35 to 39 age group categories, second highest percentage of main workers to the total migrants of Chhattisgarh were in 40 to 59 age group category and thirdly were recorded in 30 to 34 age group category and least of percentage of main worker to the total migrants of Chhattisgarh and about 40 percent of main worker migrants to the total migrants of Chhattisgarh did not count in any specific age group category.

Participation of total main workers, marginal workers and non-worker migrants:

Table 5 shows the percentage of participation of total main workers, marginal workers, and non-worker migrants of Chhattisgarh state all duration of residence by their age group categories, 2011. The highest percentage of participation of total migrants were in the age group of 40 to 59. The least percentage of participation of total migrants were in the age group of 15 to 19.

Table: 5
Chhattisgarh
Percentage of participation of total main worker, marginal worker and non-worker migrants, 2011
(All duration of Residence)

Age-group	<u>Total migrants</u>		<u>Main workers</u>		<u>Marginal Workers</u>		<u>Non-Workers</u>	
	Persons	Percentage	Persons	Percentage	Persons	Percentage	Persons	Percentage
0-14	6,60,277	9.56	13,610	0.48	14,109	1.0	6,32,558	24.0
15-19	3,80,811	5.51	89,872	3.14	71,485	5.1	2,19,454	8.3
20-24	7,37,933	10.68	2,82,877	9.88	1,96,510	14.0	2,58,546	9.8
25-29	8,23,855	11.93	3,79,681	13.26	2,12,590	15.1	2,31,584	8.8
30-34	8,29,456	12.01	4,34,408	15.17	2,07,761	14.8	1,87,287	7.1
35-39	7,65,162	11.08	4,26,232	14.89	1,78,069	12.7	1,60,861	6.1
40-59	18,82,201	27.25	10,33,092	36.08	4,07,215	29.0	4,41,894	16.7
60+	8,20,350	11.88	2,00,708	7.01	1,15,772	8.2	5,03,870	19.1
Age not stated	7,154	0.10	2,860	0.10	1,081	0.1	3,213	0.1
Total	69,07,199	100	28,63,340	100.00	14,04,592	100.0	26,39,267	100.0

In the category of main workers, the highest percentage of engagement of main migrants were of those migrants who are in the age group of 40 to 59 age and

the least percentage of participation of main workers were in the age group of 0 to 14. In the category of marginal workers, the highest percentage of participation of

marginal workers were of those migrants who were in the age group of 40 to 59 age and the least percentage of participation of marginal workers were in the age group of 0 to 14. Finally in the category of non-worker, the highest percentage of engagement of non-workers were in the age group of 0 to 14 age and the least percentage of engagement of non-workers were in the age group of 35 to 39 age. It was observed that the highest percentage of participation of total workers, main workers and marginal workers were in the age of 40-59 and the least percentage of participation of total, main and marginal workers were in the age group of 0 to 14.

Discussion and Conclusion:

In this paper we examined the working status of migrant workers in the state of Chhattisgarh, according their age group category. According to the census of India migrant workers are classified into main workers, marginal workers and non-workers. According to their skill and working experience they are engaged various types of works. This paper tries to understand the engagement of the migrants in various types of works in the state of Chhattisgarh. We were observed that the highest percentage of participation of total workers, main workers and marginal workers were in the age of 40-59 and the least percentage of participation of total, main and marginal workers were in the age

group of 0 to 14. A little number of migrants did not record in any specific age group category that means they did not tell their ages to the interviewers.

The highest number of total migrants of Chhattisgarh from all duration of residence were in 40 to 59 age group categories due to family responsibility and getting better opportunities so the age group of 40 to 59 workers migrate to one place to another place. The least number of total migrant workers of Chhattisgarh were in 15 to 19 age group categories due to the enforcement of act of child prohibition in hazardous work, the engagement of children in the age group of 0 to 14 is very less.

In case of percentage of non-workers to the total migrants the highest percentage of male non-workers were in 0 to 14 age group categories. least percentage of male non-workers were in 35 to 39 age group categories. The highest percentage of female non-workers were in 0 to 14 age group categories, least percentage of female non-workers were in 35 to 39 age group categories. The highest percentage of male main workers were in 35 to 39 age group categories and least percentage of male main workers were reported in 0 to 14 age group categories. The highest percentage of female main workers were in 35 to 39 age group category and least percentage of female

main workers were in 0 to 14 age group categories. It means the work engagement of male and female were same or equal according to their age group category in non-workers and main workers who were migrated to other place from the state of Chhattisgarh.

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